

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON INFORMATICS VISUALIZATION

journal homepage : www.joiv.org/index.php/joiv

Understanding Performance Efficiency in ISO/IEC 25000: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract—Performance efficiency is a critical aspect of software quality, particularly in modern applications handling large data volumes, simultaneous users, and complex operations. This study aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of current research on performance efficiency under ISO/IEC 25010. This involved examining the topics driving this research, alongside their contexts, objectives, applications, tools, and metrics, enabling the visualization of emerging trends in the quantification and evaluation of performance efficiency. To this end, a systematic literature review was conducted from 2014 to 2024, following a protocol that combined automated and manual searches. This process yielded 38 primary studies. The results revealed five central research topics, with time behavior identified as the most studied sub-characteristic (48%), followed by resource utilization (36%) and capacity (16%). The study also analyzed the reasons for this distribution of research interest. A total of 68 metrics were identified: 41 related to time behavior, 16 to resource utilization, and 11 to capacity. Additionally, 46 tools were identified for evaluating these three sub-characteristics. This analysis provides a solid foundation for objectively measuring and comparing software performance. The findings of this study offer a holistic view of performance efficiency. From an academic perspective, it supports the development and validation of research in software engineering. It provides a comprehensive understanding of ISO/IEC 25010, facilitating systematic improvements and tracking its evolution. From an industry perspective, it serves as a practical resource for enhancing competitiveness by promoting compliance with the standard and improving knowledge of performance efficiency.

Keywords—ISO/IEC 25000; 25010; SQuaRE; performance efficiency; performance evaluation; time behavior; resource utilization; capacity; quality software.

Manuscript received 5 Sep. 2024; revised 16 Dec. 2024; accepted 14 Jan. 2025. Date of publication 30 Nov. 2025. International Journal on Informatics Visualization is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International License.

I. INTRODUCTION

Software quality models are frameworks encompassing a set of criteria, attributes, and the relationships among them. These components are essential for determining quality [1]. In the field of software development, ISO/IEC 25000—also known as Software Product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE)—is widely recognized as the standard for software quality assessment [2], [3], [4]. This model provides a structured framework for assessing software quality and is divided into five sections that systematically address different aspects of quality. The 2501n division, known as the Quality Model Division, defines the internal, external, and in-use quality attributes of software products [5]. Within this division, ISO/IEC 25010—the Product Quality Model—specifies the quality characteristics and sub-characteristics for assessing software products [6].

ISO/IEC 25010 is a fundamental standard in the software development industry, providing a detailed and robust framework for evaluating software quality [7], [8]. Performance efficiency, an attribute of ISO/IEC 25010, represents the performance of a product relative to the amount of resources utilized under specified conditions [2]. This attribute is further characterized by three sub-characteristics: 1) Time behavior: The capability of a product to perform its specified functions under given conditions while ensuring that its response times and throughput rates meet predefined requirements. 2) Resource utilization: The capability of a product to use no more than the specified number of resources to perform its functions under specified conditions. 3) Capacity: The capability of a product to meet requirements for the maximum limits of a product parameter.

Performance efficiency plays a crucial role in business environments and the software industry by influencing scalability, workload management capacity [9], market

competitiveness [10], and user experience [11], [12]. Despite its significance, there are no detailed, systematic studies that provide software industry professionals, developers, and researchers with comprehensive insights into the current state of this construct. Such investigations would allow these professionals to identify areas of active investigation and understand the evolution of the standard.

The key contributions of this study include enhancing understanding of performance efficiency within a comprehensive framework of its sub-characteristics, thereby establishing a robust foundation for the comparison, measurement, and improvement of software performance across diverse contexts. This includes identifying technical trends and their implications for business competitiveness and user satisfaction. Furthermore, by providing a thorough analysis of existing evaluation methods and their outcomes, this study serves as a guiding reference for future updates to the ISO/IEC 25010 standard.

A. Objectives and Research Questions

The objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the current landscape of performance efficiency, as defined by ISO/IEC 25000. Specifically, the study aims to identify research topics driving investigations in this area, including their contexts, objectives, and applications, as well as the measurement and evaluation methods used. These objectives form the basis for the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1. What are the main studies on performance efficiency under the ISO/IEC 25010 standard, and which research topics do they address?
- RQ2. Which sub-characteristics of performance efficiency, as defined by ISO/IEC 25010, are emphasized in current research?
- RQ3. What metrics are used to assess performance efficiency under the ISO/IEC 25010 standard?
- RQ4. What are the most commonly used tools for evaluating performance efficiency under the ISO/IEC 25010 standard?
- RQ5: What is the current status of performance efficiency implementation, and what recommendations can be made for future work?

B. Identifying the Necessity for a Performance Efficiency Study

Software has become an essential and pervasive element in modern society, integrating into nearly all human activities. In many cases, it serves as a critical asset for the sustainability of diverse disciplines and ecosystems. The construction of software is a complex process, as it is not manufactured but instead developed within dynamic, intricate, and ever-changing environments. Consequently, ensuring software quality is essential for multiple reasons: 1) Technical reasons: Ensuring quality helps make software reliable, capable of functioning correctly under varied conditions, compliant with security standards to maintain data consistency, and maintainable to support scalability [13]. 2) Commercial reasons: High-quality software provides a competitive advantage and serves as an effective business support tool, enhancing its market value. 3) Regulatory and cost-related

reasons: Ensuring quality ensures compliance with legal regulations and reduces costs associated with quality issues throughout the software's life cycle [14].

Within the ISO/IEC 25010 standard, performance efficiency is one of the most frequently addressed research topics [15]. It is also considered one of the most impactful factors influencing software quality [16], [17], [18].

Performance efficiency influences both the managerial and technical aspects of an organization [19], [20]. From a managerial perspective, it aids in planning the acquisition of hardware resources to meet processing performance demands, determining maximum loads and peak demands, and selecting appropriate technologies to support organizational systems.

From a technical perspective, performance efficiency impacts software architecture [21], [22], which coordinates and facilitates communication among its components to meet technical and operational requirements [23]. This includes optimizing component design, scalability, and load balancing to ensure effective resource management. Additionally, response times must be assessed in environments such as cloud applications, distributed systems, and systems that involve large numbers of users simultaneously.

The effects of performance efficiency extend to backend and frontend development. Key areas for optimization include database query management, memory management, resource compression and minification during code development, document object model optimization for web applications, state and request management, thread and process handling, and the use of microservices, parallel programming, and decoupling in assessments.

For applications targeting end users or external audiences, performance efficiency is a decisive factor in determining user experience. This includes ensuring fast loading times, seamless interactivity, and consistent navigation. In mobile applications, performance efficiency is particularly critical owing to the limited resources of mobile devices, such as memory, battery, and CPU capacity (or their future equivalents).

Overall, performance efficiency is relevant not only to the software industry that implements these solutions but also to organizations that acquire or develop them. Indirectly, it also affects end users, who evaluate hardware performance based on resource consumption requirements, capacity limits, and temporal performance.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A systematic literature review is a methodology used for analyzing existing scientific contributions on a topic and integrating them into the broader field of knowledge [24]. Its objective is to summarize and integrate current knowledge, consolidating the existing body of literature within a particular field. This methodology guides researchers into new or less-explored fields and helps them evaluate the novelty and originality of their projects and research efforts. A systematic literature review thus offers an updated and comprehensive overview of the evolution of a topic, enabling the establishment of solid definitions and foundational bases for future research [25].

Fig. 1 Research-guided review protocol based on [26]

A. Review Protocol

This section details our review protocol, which is based on the methodology adopted in [26] and is illustrated in Fig. 1. The protocol comprises five stages. 1) Identification of research questions: This stage involved defining the research questions for the study. 2) Search strategy and article selection: A systematic approach was developed to identify, evaluate, and select relevant literature that addresses the research questions. 3) Data extraction: This stage involved extracting specific data to address the study's objectives. Notably, the objectives for this stage focused on performance efficiency. Although performance efficiency has been primarily considered alongside other attributes in previous research articles, its inclusion in these articles enabled it to be analyzed in this research. 4) Data synthesis and result extraction: In this stage, the extracted data were synthesized, leading to the identification of relevant conclusions drawn from the studies. 5) Reporting: All findings from the research were documented and presented in this final stage.

B. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The objective of this study was to understand the construct of performance efficiency, focusing on its evolution as defined by ISO/IEC 25010. Specifically, the study examined the most frequently studied characteristics and sub-characteristics related to performance efficiency, as well as the metrics and tools used to evaluate them. To this end, the following inclusion criteria were established: The articles must be published between 2014 and June 2024. They must be peer-reviewed. They must address the research questions

outlined in this study. Finally, the articles must be indexed in the Scopus database.

C. Search Strategy

This study focused on performance efficiency as an attribute of ISO/IEC 25010. The search string was structured in two parts: The first focused on the standard, including the attribute, and the second focused on the attribute itself. These parts were connected using the "AND" operator, while key terms within each part were linked using the "OR" operator.

The final search string was: ("iso 25000" OR "iso 25010" OR "ISO/IEC 25010" OR "ISO/IEC 25000") AND ("performance efficiency" OR "performance evaluation"). This search string was applied to the Scopus database, yielding 63 results. A complete manual review of these selected articles was conducted, analyzing their titles, abstracts, and keywords to identify those that address the performance efficiency attribute in ISO/IEC 25010. However, not all articles answered our research questions, and in many cases, performance efficiency was studied alongside other characteristics of the standard. Consequently, a thorough analysis of the full text of each article was performed, ultimately resulting in 31 relevant articles.

Next, a backward search, also known as a chain search [27], was performed. This involved examining the references cited in the 31 selected articles to identify earlier studies that could provide additional insights into the topic. This step added four more articles, bringing the total to 35. Subsequently, a forward search was conducted to find more recent studies. This method sought articles that cited the 31 initially selected articles and the four additional articles from

the backward search. Ultimately, the forward search yielded three new articles, bringing the total to 38 primary studies.

D. Data Extraction Process

During this stage, each article was thoroughly analyzed in light of our research questions. The extracted data are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I
DATA EXTRACTED FROM THE PRIMARY STUDIES

Extracted data	Description
Id	Unique identifier for each item
Title	Title of the study
Year /Country	Year of publication, and the country of the first author's affiliation
Context	The specific environment or area where the research was conducted
Objective	The main objective of the study is to investigate the performance efficiency attribute
Research Strategy	Research approaches, such as experiments, multiple case studies, reviews, or surveys
Methodology	Research methodologies used, such as quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-method approaches
Data Collection Methods	Methods used to collect data, such as software testing, questionnaires, or performance testing
Tool	Tools used to measure performance efficiency
Sub-characteristics of ISO 25010	Resource utilization, time behavior, and capacity
Metrics	Quantitative measures are used to evaluate the quality or progress of performance efficiency
Subject	The set or system where the methods were applied
Theme	Thematic classification of the study's focus area

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The selected studies focus on performance efficiency in accordance with ISO/IEC 25010. While performance efficiency is not always the primary subject of these articles—often appearing alongside other attributes—they still provide relevant insights for addressing the research questions.

A. Data Extraction

1) *Word Cloud*: Fig. 2 presents a word cloud of primary studies, generated from their titles and abstracts using NVivo 14 software. The most frequently occurring words include "performance," "quality," "application," "25010," "software," and "system," reflecting the main constructs addressed in these works.

Fig. 2 Word cloud of the primary studies

2) *Sources of Publications*: The publication sources of the primary studies are illustrated in Fig. 3. These include 14 conference papers, 19 journal articles, 2 book series entries, 2 seminar studies, and 1 symposium paper.

Fig. 3 Sources of primary publications

3) *Publication Date*: Fig. 4 illustrates the evolution of studies on performance efficiency over time, with the highest number of publications occurring between 2019 and 2022.

Fig. 4 Publication dates of the primary studies

4) *Country of Publications*: Fig. 5 presents the countries of affiliation of the first authors of the selected studies. Indonesia leads in publications on performance efficiency, followed by the Philippines, Ecuador, Bangladesh, and Brazil. Other countries, including the United Kingdom, Peru, Ghana, and Mexico, each have one publication.

Fig. 5 Countries of origin of publications, based on the affiliation of their authors

5) *Research Context*: Fig. 6 highlights the contexts in which performance efficiency studies were conducted. Augmented reality research predominates, followed by university academic systems and enterprise resource planning

systems. Additionally, smaller numbers of studies span diverse industries and fields of knowledge.

Fig. 6 Application contexts of the selected studies

TABLE II
CLASSIFICATION OF THE THEMES OF THE PRIMARY STUDIES

Theme ID	Performance efficiency theme	Description
1	Performance efficiency evaluation	This theme encompasses articles focusing on the performance efficiency of applications, information systems, individual components, underlying infrastructure, or other software-related elements. These studies address the question: How is the performance efficiency of software evaluated?
2	Proposal of models for evaluating performance efficiency	This category includes articles presenting models designed to evaluate performance efficiency. These articles answer the question: How can a model be developed to evaluate the performance efficiency of software?
3	Proposal of performance efficiency metrics	Studies in this category focus on defining new metrics or refining existing ones to evaluate performance efficiency. They address the question: How should metrics be constructed to assess software performance efficiency?
4	Relationship of performance efficiency with functional and non-functional software requirements	This group explores how software requirements relate to the ISO/IEC 25010 quality attributes, with a particular focus on performance efficiency. These studies answer the question: How can the relationship between functional and non-functional requirements and performance efficiency be identified?
5	Relationship of performance efficiency with environmental sustainability goals	Articles in this category investigate how software can support sustainability objectives. These studies answer the question: What is the relationship between performance efficiency and the requirements for achieving sustainable software?

Fig. 7 Distribution of main topics in performance efficiency studies

B. RQ1. What are the Main Studies on Performance Efficiency Under the ISO/IEC 25010 Standard, and Which Research Topics do They Address?

The central theme of a study refers to the primary topic or subject that guides the research [28]. The authors of this review identified and categorized key topics from each selected article by focusing on the main themes and specific research objectives related to performance efficiency under the ISO/IEC 25010 standard. The primary study topics derived from this search are presented in Table II.

The distribution of these study topics is illustrated in Fig. 7. Performance efficiency evaluation is the most extensively studied topic, accounting for 79% of the total papers. Proposals for models to evaluate performance efficiency represent 5% of the total papers, while proposals for performance efficiency metrics account for 10%. The remaining topics, including the relationships between performance efficiency and functional/non-functional software requirements and between performance efficiency and environmental sustainability goals, each constitute 3%, making them the least-studied areas.

Fig. 8 illustrates the methodologies and research strategies used across these research themes. Performance efficiency evaluation, as the dominant theme, comprises 28 quantitative studies, 1 descriptive study, and 1 mixed-method study. The research strategies for this theme are predominantly single case studies (16), followed by multiple case studies (eight), experiments (two), and surveys (four). For the remaining themes, methodologies such as review studies, experiments, and mixed methods are also observed. Among research strategies, multiple case studies appear most frequently.

Fig. 8 Research methodologies and strategies of performance efficiency research

C. RQ2. Which Sub-Characteristics of Performance Efficiency, as Defined by ISO/IEC 25010, are Emphasized in Current Research?

The sub-characteristics of performance efficiency, as defined by ISO/IEC 25010, are time behavior, resource utilization, and capacity. Fig. 9 illustrates the distribution of these sub-characteristics across the selected articles. Time behavior is the most studied, appearing in 34 of the selected articles, or 48% of the total papers. Resource utilization follows, accounting for 36% (25 studies), while capacity accounts for 16% (11 studies).

Fig. 9 Distribution of performance efficiency studies based on sub-characteristics

Time behavior, the most emphasized sub-characteristic appearing in 48% of the selected articles, was examined from multiple perspectives, including: Determining whether the software maintains high performance across all states [29], [30], assessing real-time information delivery [31], evaluating loading times [32], [33], [34], [35], [36] and ensuring high loading speed even during simultaneous transactions [37], [31], determining the time required for task processing [38], [39], [40], [41], [42], recording server connection times [43], identifying the maximum time or speed to execute tasks [44],

and analyzing response times under certain conditions [45], [46]. Additionally, some studies specifically compared the evaluation of time behavior on mobile devices versus desktop devices [47], [45].

Resource utilization, the second-most-studied sub-characteristic, was addressed in 36% of the selected articles. These articles focused on efficient resource usage [29], along with an application's overall resource consumption [48], [49], [50], [51], [52], [53], [54], [55] and resource utilization [56], [57], [58], [59].

Capacity was the least studied sub-characteristic, appearing in only 16% of the primary studies. This finding aligns with the observations reported in [17], [60]. The studies considering capacity primarily explored the maximum resource limits an application can handle [61], [17], the number of simultaneous functions the software can execute [62], [63], and the maximum number of users that can work in parallel [55].

D. RQ3. What Metrics are used to Assess Performance Efficiency under the ISO/IEC 25010 Standard?

The metrics used to evaluate performance efficiency were classified based on sub-characteristics, as depicted in Fig. 10. The 38 primary studies identified a total of 68 distinct metrics. Time behavior is the most studied sub-characteristic, encompassing 41 metrics. The most frequently explored metric is response time, appearing in 11 studies, followed by loading time (9 studies) and performance score (4 studies). Additionally, 15 other metrics are grouped under "others," with each metric studied in only one investigation. Resource utilization is the second-most-studied sub-characteristic, with 16 metrics. The most prominent metrics in this category are memory usage (16 studies), followed by CPU usage (15 studies) and storage utilization (3 studies). Finally, the capacity metrics include 11 metrics, each of which was studied only once in the primary studies.

Fig. 8 Metrics for evaluating each performance efficiency sub-characteristic

E. RQ4. What are the Most Commonly used Tools for Evaluating Performance Efficiency under the ISO/IEC 25010 Standard?

The tools used to evaluate performance efficiency varied substantially across the selected studies, totaling 46. The most widely used tool is GTMetrix, used in 7 studies, followed by Apptim, a paid tool used in 4 studies. Other tools include free tools such as WebPageTest, PageSpeed Insights, JMeter, CPU-Z, CPU Meter, CPU Indicator, All-In-One Toolbox, Memory Info, and the Cucumber framework, which offers both free and paid versions, each appearing in two studies. Additionally, 10 tools were mentioned in only one study each. Overall, most of these tools focus on assessing hardware-related metrics such as CPU usage, RAM consumption, load times, and the performance of software processes, computational tasks, and the overall system. These correspond primarily to the sub-characteristics of resource utilization and time behavior. Tools specifically used to assess system capacity include Apptim, Little Eye, Odo, Cucumber, and the Mocha framework.

F. RQ5: What is the Current Status of Performance Efficiency Implementation, and What Recommendations can be Made for Future Work?

This systematic literature review of the performance efficiency attribute of the ISO/IEC 25010 standard aims to understand its current status, given its influence on software quality and end-user satisfaction.

In terms of software quality, performance efficiency plays a critical role in defining software architecture. It determines how components communicate, the resources and time required for these communications, and the allocation of functionalities. Efficient resource utilization can reduce operating costs. Furthermore, performance efficiency is closely linked to software reliability and stability, as poorly managed resources can lead to system crashes and failures, negatively affecting processes and outcomes.

Time behavior has gained prominence as the prevalence of applications requiring real-time responses increases, including financial systems, video games, and online communication platforms. Modern users' expectations for

near-instant performance have further driven research in this area. Additionally, most primary studies were conducted within commercial, academic, or government contexts, with a strong focus on end-user satisfaction. From a user experience perspective, time behavior has an immediate, perceptible impact, as it ensures that the software responds quickly to user actions.

Another key observation is the availability of a wide range of tools, both free and paid, for evaluating time behavior and resource utilization. These tools facilitate the quick diagnosis of system behavior and performance, identification of bottlenecks, and implementation of timely solutions. Additionally, these sub-characteristics benefit from well-defined metrics. For time behavior, these metrics support the implementation of automated tests to consistently evaluate temporal performance. Meanwhile, for resource utilization, these metrics enable the assessment and optimization of resource consumption, resulting in improved operational efficiency and cost savings.

Concerning relevance in application contexts, time behavior remains a constant focus of evaluation across systems ranging from embedded systems to cloud services and complex distributed systems. In these fields, fast, consistent response times are critical for nearly all types of software. In contrast, resource utilization is essential in environments with limited or expensive resources, such as mobile devices, embedded systems, and data center servers.

The capacity sub-characteristic is the least studied. As noted in the discussion of RQ2, this finding aligns with previous research, in which target audiences expressed less interest in capacity. Capacity refers to the software's ability to handle increasing data processing demands and simultaneous users without performance degradation. However, users typically interact with software under normal operating conditions, where extreme loads or excessive simultaneous users are uncommon. While capacity is crucial for scalability and managing high loads, its impact on user experience is more indirect and less perceptible in daily use. Furthermore, evaluating capacity is complex, requiring large-scale tests with concurrent users, which are both costly and labor-intensive. This systematic review also highlights the

limited availability of metrics and tools for measuring capacity.

Regarding the current research landscape, performance efficiency remains a critical feature of the ISO/IEC 25010 standard and is expected to continue evolving. This is due to its direct connections to operating system performance [64], [65], economic impacts on organizations [66], [67], [68], resource consumption reduction [69], and user satisfaction [70], [71]. Its criticality is also attributed to its relationship with software quality [72], [73], [74].

Performance efficiency also affects software development methodologies, such as Agile [75], [76], [77] and DevOps [78], [79]. These methodologies have accelerated software development cycles, presenting challenges for maintaining and improving performance efficiency in systems with distributed architectures and real-time data consumption. Additionally, as the demands for big data management and machine learning integration in software systems increase, performance efficiency must ensure smooth operations without overloading systems.

This work delineates several future challenges pertinent to the study of this attribute. Among these is the optimization of

performance efficiency through emerging technologies such as big data, artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and distributed real-time systems. Current primary studies predominantly focus on applications within academic, business, or augmented reality contexts. Additionally, there is a need for deeper exploration of efficiency in devices with constrained resources, such as mobile equipment. Another avenue for investigation pertains to the sub-characteristic of capacity, which remains underexplored. This presents an opportunity for developing tools and metrics to examine how systems can manage increasing workloads without compromising performance—an essential consideration in environments anticipating high levels of concurrent users. Furthermore, an area that warrants further inquiry is the relationship between performance efficiency and environmental sustainability. This emerging field requires greater attention, particularly in today's context, where sustainable development is prioritized.

The summary of the findings is presented in Table III. The column Theme ID refers to the column Theme ID in Table II, Classification of the themes of the primary studies.

TABLE III
PRIMARY STUDIES

ID	Ref.	(Year)/ Country	Context	Research Strategy/ Method	Data Collection Technique	Tool	Sub- characteristics of ISO 25010	Metrics	Theme ID
1	[40]	(2020)/ Indonesia	University academic system	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software. Observation	Not clear	Time behavior Resource utilization	Loading time CPU and memory usage	1
2	[41]	(2020)/ Indonesia	E-commerce	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Questionnaire and test of data extracted from the websites	Fuzzy Mandani algorithm, Fuzzy classification, Particle Swarm Optimization	Resource utilization	No defined	2
3	[29]	(2019)/ Indonesia	Industry	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	GQM (Goal Question Metrics) method	Not clear	Time behavior Resource utilization	Screen first loading time, screen resume loading time, and API device execution CPU and memory usage	3
4	[45]	(2024)/ Philippines	Policies	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Test of data extracted from the websites	WebPageTest, Google Lighthouse, PageSpeed Insights, Yellow Lab, and Pingdom	Time behavior	First View, Server Configuration, Time to First Byte, Start Render, First Contentful Paint, Speed Index, Largest Contentful Paint, Cumulative Layout Shift, Total Blocking Time, Page Weight, Requests, DOM Complexity, JS Complexity, Bad JS, jQuery, CSS Complexity, Bad CSS, Web Fonts	1
5	[45]	(2019)/ Ecuador	Augmented reality	Experiment/ Quantitative	Observation. Test	CPU Gauge, CPU Meter, CPU-X, CPU- Indicator, CPU-Z, Game Booster, All- InOne Toolbox, Antutu, Memory info, and hardware information	Time behavior Resource utilization Capacity	Response time, waiting time, performance in a unit of time Lines of code, CPU, I/O, and memory usage, Number of online requests, number of simultaneous accesses, number of simultaneous bandwidths	1
6	[38]	(2022)/ London	Environment	Experiment/ Mixed-method	Inductive method. Mixed-method	Software tools, Expert consultations, training material, and other files	Time behavior Resource utilization	Calculation of time used per task Evaluation of the resources needed to perform the task	1
7	[46]	(2023)/ Indonesia	University academic/ administrative system	Single case study/ Quantitative	Questionnaire and data extracted from the websites	Custom software created	Time behavior	Time response	1
8	[48]	(2022)/ Perú	Pet	Single case study/ Descriptive	Observation. Test	Software Firebase	Time behavior Resource utilization	Application startup time, graphical statistics CPU, memory, and internet usage	1

ID	Ref.	(Year)/ Country	Context	Research Strategy/ Method	Data Collection Technique	Tool	Sub- characteristics of ISO 25010	Metrics	Theme ID
9	[56]	(2021)/ Indonesia	Augmented reality	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Observation. Test	Not clear	Time behavior Resource utilization	Threads Usage Testing CPU and memory usage	1
10	[17]	(2021)/ Indonesia	Health	Single case study/ Quantitative	Observation. Test	Black Box Testing	Time behavior Resource utilization	Response time, y processing time when performing a function RAM usage	1
						Apptim Software	Capacity	Maximum RAM usage	
11	[31]	(2020)/ Philippines	Restaurant	Survey/ Quantitative	Questionnaire	No defined	Time behavior Resource utilization	Information update time, loading time in simultaneous transactions Handle an amount of data	1
12	[30]	(2020)/ Ghana	ERP	No clear/ Review	Secondary data (Quality models)	No clear	Time behavior Resource utilization	Quick processes to events Efficient use of resources	3
							Capacity	System parameters aligned with requested requirements	
13	[57]	(2020)/ Indonesia	University academic/administrat ive system	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test of data extracted from the websites	GTmetrix	Time behavior	Page speed score, load time	1
14	[61]	(2019)/ Indonesia	Augmented reality	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Observation. Test	Little Eye Testdroid	Capacity Resource utilization	Maximum CPU usage CPU and memory usage	1
15	[37]	(2014)/ Indonesia	Mobile thick client	Multiple case study/ Experiment	GQM (Goal Question Metrics) method	Not clear	Resource utilization Time behavior	CPU and memory usage, network usage Screen first loading time, screen resume loading time	3
16	[58]	(2023)/ Indonesia	IoT	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software. Observation	GTmetrix	Time behavior	No defined	1
17	[16]	(2021)/ Bangladesh	ERP	Survey/ Quantitative	Questionnaire	No defined	Time behavior Resource utilization Capacity	No defined	1
18	[55]	(2020)/ Indonesia	Automation testing	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Test page, Page Object Pattern	Cucumber, Mocha Framework	Time behavior Resource utilization Capacity	Mean response time, Turnaround Time Conformance, Throughput Conformance Response Time, Mean Turnaround Time Actual processor time, operation time, memory used, the duration of the I / O device on busy and performance of the task, and the storage used on the device. User access conformance, user access increase	1
19	[54]	(2024)/ Ecuador	Web application developed in JavaScript frameworks	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Test software; adding, updating, and loading 500 rows	JMeter and Chrome DevTools toolkit	Time behavior Resource utilization	Loading time and responsiveness of the user interface Memory usage, GPU memory	1
20	[44]	(2022)/ Philippines	Machine vision	Survey/ Quantitative	Questionnaire	No defined	Time behavior	Image classification speed	1
21	[32]	(2022)/ Indonesia	University academic/administrat ive system	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software	GTmetrix	Time behavior	Response time	1
22	[42]	(2022)/ Indonesia	Augmented reality	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software	Chronometer	Time behavior	Response time	1
23	[53]	(2021)/ Indonesia	University academic/administrat ive system	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software	Google Stackdriver	Time behavior Resource utilization	Response latency CPU and memory usage	1
24	[52]	(2019)/ Indonesia	Religion	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software	AWS Device Farm tool in automation	Time behavior Resource utilization	Thread execution CPU and memory usage	1
25	[51]	(2019)/ Indonesia	Augmented reality	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software	AppAchi	Time behavior Resource utilization	Thread execution CPU and memory usage	1
26	[33]	(2019)/ Indonesia	Educational game application	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software	GTmetrix	Time behavior	Page Speed score, YSlow	1
27	[34]	(2019)/Indone sia	University academic/ administrative system	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software	GTmetrix	Time behavior	Page speed score, YSlow, response time	1

ID	Ref.	(Year)/ Country	Context	Research Strategy/ Method	Data Collection Technique	Tool	Sub- characteristics of ISO 25010	Metrics	Theme ID
28	[39]	(2019)/ Brazil	Financial organization	Review/ Review	No defined	NVivo	Time behavior Resource utilization Capacity	Response time, maximum time, and average time No defined Must support	4
29	[20]	(2018)/ Mexico	Sustainability area	Review/ Systematic mapping study	No defined	No defined	Time behavior Resource utilization	Sending of small HTTP packets Memoization, memory and cache usage, compressing file streams, execution in the background of irrelevant applications	5
30	[35]	(2023)/ Indonesia	Football tournaments and leagues	Single case study/ Quantitative	Test software	GTmetrix	Time behavior	Performance score, load time	1
31	[62]	(2023)/ Indonesia	ERP	Single case study/ Quantitative	Stress tests	Odoo	Capacity Time behavior	Services that can be performed simultaneously Number of requests	1
32	[50]	(2022)/ Indonesia	News portal	Survey/ Quantitative	Questionnaire	No defined	Time behavior Resource utilization Capacity	No defined	1
33	[59]	(2022)/ Indonesia	REST API	Single case study, Survey/ Mixed- method	Performance testing, Questionnaire	Postman, Katalon, SoapUI, JMeter, Insomnia, JBehave and Cucumber frameworks	Resource utilization	Mean Processor Utilization, Mean Memory Utilization, Mean I/O Utilization, Storage Utilization, Bandwidth Utilization	2
34	[49]	(2020)/ Ecuador	Augmented reality	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Performance testing	All-InOne, Antutu, CPU Meter, CPU Indicator, CPU-Z, Toolbox, Memory info, Hardware Information	Resource utilization	CPU and memory usage	1
35	[60]	(2024)/ Indonesia	Financial organization	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Black Box Testing Stress testing	Black box testing, Test project Tool Apptim Software Apptim Software	Time behavior Resource utilization Capacity	No defined	1
36	[47]	(2022)/ Indonesia	Restaurant	Single case study/ Quantitative	Performance testing	Dareboost	Time behavior	Time to first byte, DOM content loaded event, visually complete, speed index, fully loaded, reload, largest contentful paint, total blocking time, cumulative layout shift, DOM complete, DOM interactive, time to interactive, first contentful paint, start render	1
37	[36]	(2021)/ Bangladesh	E-commerce	Multiple case study/ Quantitative	Performance testing	WebpageTest, Gtmetrix, Page Speed	Time behavior	Load Time, First Byte, Start Render, First Contentful Paint, Speed Index, Largest Contentful Paint, Cumulative Layout Shift, Total Blocking Time, and Time to Interactive parameters	1
38	[63]	(2015)/Brazil	SOA	Survey/ Quantitative	Questionnaire	No defined	Time behavior Resource utilization Capacity	Response and processing times, and throughput rates of a system Processor capacity, memory usage, disk capacity, and network bandwidth Availability of a service even with many simultaneous accesses.	3

IV. CONCLUSION

This systematic literature review examined the performance efficiency characteristic of the ISO/IEC 25010 standard. The study reviewed 38 primary studies, focusing on their application contexts, objectives, research strategies, methodologies, data collection methods, tools used, sub-characteristics analyzed, and central themes. These themes include performance efficiency evaluation, proposals for

models to evaluate performance efficiency, proposals for performance efficiency metrics, the relationship between performance efficiency and functional or non-functional software requirements, and the relationship between performance efficiency and environmental sustainability goals.

The findings revealed that time behavior is the most studied sub-characteristic, accounting for 48% of the primary studies, followed by resource utilization at 36% and capacity at 16%. This study also explored the reasons underlying this

distribution of research interest. A total of 68 metrics were identified, with 41 related to time behavior, 16 to resource utilization, and 11 to capacity. Additionally, 46 tools were utilized to evaluate these three sub-characteristics across the selected studies.

Nonetheless, there are limitations about the findings derived from this analysis. The review was based exclusively on studies published between 2014 and 2024, potentially omitting relevant research conducted outside this timeframe or not indexed in the databases used. Additionally, the practices employed in the software industry to measure performance efficiency are sparsely documented due to the limited collaboration between academia and the software development sector. Some selected studies integrate performance efficiency within broader investigations, which may restrict the depth of analysis in specific areas. Moreover, variability in study quality exists, with significant differences in methodology, data quality, and tools employed, which could introduce bias into specific results or interpretations.

The study also presents an updated perspective on the current state of research on performance efficiency and its three attributes. It highlights the reasons time, behavior, and resource utilization are more widely studied and valued, as well as the future challenges these attributes are likely to face.

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